

On the hybrid mean value of the Smarandache kn -digital sequence and Smarandache function ¹

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the hybrid mean value properties of the Smarandache kn -digital sequence and Smarandache function, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords Smarandache kn -digital sequence, Smarandache function, hybrid mean value, asymptotic formula, elementary method.

§1. Introduction

For any positive integer k , the famous Smarandache kn -digital sequence $a(k, n)$ is defined as all positive integers which can be partitioned into two groups such that the second part is k times bigger than the first. For example, Smarandache $2n$ and $3n$ digital sequences $a(2, n)$ and $a(3, n)$ are defined as $\{a(2, n)\} = \{12, 24, 36, 48, 510, 612, 714, 816, \dots\}$ and $\{a(3, n)\} = \{13, 26, 39, 412, 515, 618, 721, 824, \dots\}$.

Recently, Professor Gou Su told me that she studied the hybrid mean value properties of the Smarandache kn -digital sequence and the divisor sum function $\sigma(n)$, and proved that the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\sigma(n)}{a(k, n)} = \frac{3\pi^2}{k \cdot 20 \cdot \ln 10} \cdot \ln x + O(1)$$

holds for all integers $1 \leq k \leq 9$.

When I read professor Gou Su's work, I found that the method is very new, and the results are also interesting. This paper as a note of Gou Su's work, we consider the hybrid mean value properties of the Smarandache kn -digital sequence and Smarandache function $S(n)$, which is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n|m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n|m!, m \in \mathbb{N}\}$. In this paper, we will use the elementary and analytic methods to study a similar problem, and prove a new conclusion. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. Let $1 \leq k \leq 9$, then for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(k, n)} = \frac{3\pi^2}{k \cdot 20} \cdot \ln \ln x + O(1).$$

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§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall use the elementary and combinational methods to complete the proof of our theorem. First we need following:

Lemma. For any real number $x > 1$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{n} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} \cdot \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

Proof. For any real number $x > 2$, from [4] we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} S(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right). \tag{1}$$

Then from Euler summation formula (see theorem 3.1 of [3]) we can deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 < n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{n} &= \frac{1}{x} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right) \right) + \int_1^x \left(\frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{t^2}{\ln t} + O\left(\frac{t^2}{\ln^2 t}\right) \frac{1}{t^2} \right) dt \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right) + \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x}{\ln x} + \frac{13\pi^2}{12} \int_1^x \frac{1}{\ln^2 t} dt \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{6} \cdot \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This proves our Lemma.

Now we take $k = 2$ (or $k = 4$), then for any real number $x > 1$, there exists a positive integer M such that

$$5 \cdot 10^M \leq x < 5 \cdot 10^{M+1},$$

then we can deduce that

$$M = \frac{1}{\ln 10} \cdot \ln x + O(1). \tag{2}$$

So from the definition of $a(2, n)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} &= \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} + \sum_{n=5}^{49} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} + \sum_{n=50}^{499} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} + \dots + \sum_{n=5 \cdot 10^{M-1}}^{5 \cdot 10^M - 1} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} \\ &\quad + \sum_{5 \cdot 10^M \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10 + 2)} + \sum_{n=5}^{49} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^2 + 2)} + \sum_{n=50}^{499} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^3 + 2)} + \dots \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=5 \cdot 10^{M-1}}^{5 \cdot 10^M - 1} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^{M+1} + 2)} + \sum_{5 \cdot 10^M \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^{M+2} + 2)} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{1 \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} &= \sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} + \sum_{n=3}^{24} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} + \sum_{n=25}^{249} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} + \cdots + \sum_{n=\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{M-1}}^{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^M - 1} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} \\
&\quad + \sum_{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^M \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10 + 4)} + \sum_{n=3}^{24} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^2 + 4)} + \sum_{n=25}^{249} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^3 + 4)} + \cdots \\
&\quad + \sum_{n=\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{M-1}}^{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^M - 1} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^M + 4)} + \sum_{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^M \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^{M+1} + 4)}. \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

Then from (2), (3) and Lemma we may immediately deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=5 \cdot 10^{k-1}}^{5 \cdot 10^k - 1} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^{k+1} + 2)} &= \sum_{n \leq 5 \cdot 10^{k-1}} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^{k+1} + 2)} - \sum_{n \leq 5 \cdot 10^{k-1}} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^{k+1} + 2)} \\
&= \frac{\pi^2}{6} \cdot \frac{5 \cdot 10^k - 5 \cdot 10^{k-1}}{10^{k+1} + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{\ln(5 \cdot 10^k)} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right) \\
&= \frac{3\pi^2}{40} \cdot \frac{1}{k} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right) \tag{5}
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{k-1}}^{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^k - 1} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^k + 4)} &= \sum_{n \leq \frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{k-1}} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^k + 4)} - \sum_{n \leq \frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{k-1}} \frac{S(n)}{n \cdot (10^k + 4)} \\
&= \frac{\pi^2}{6} \cdot \frac{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^k - \frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{k-1}}{10^k + 4} \cdot \frac{1}{\ln(\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^k)} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right) \\
&= \frac{3\pi^2}{80} \cdot \frac{1}{k} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right). \tag{6}
\end{aligned}$$

Noting that the identity $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \pi^2/6$ and the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{1 \leq k \leq M} \frac{1}{k} = \ln M + \gamma + O\left(\frac{1}{M}\right),$$

where γ is the Euler constant.

From (2), (3) and (5) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} &= \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} + \sum_{n=5}^{49} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} + \sum_{n=50}^{499} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} + \cdots + \sum_{n=5 \cdot 10^{M-1}}^{5 \cdot 10^M - 1} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} \\ &\quad + \sum_{5 \cdot 10^M \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(2, n)} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{3\pi^2}{40} \cdot \frac{1}{k} + O\left(\sum_{k=1}^M \frac{1}{k^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{3\pi^2}{40} \ln \ln x + O(1). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} &= \sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} + \sum_{n=3}^{24} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} + \sum_{n=25}^{249} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} + \cdots + \sum_{n=\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^{M-1}}^{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^M - 1} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} \\ &\quad + \sum_{\frac{1}{4} \cdot 10^M \leq n \leq x} \frac{S(n)}{a(4, n)} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{3\pi^2}{80} \cdot \frac{1}{k} + O\left(\sum_{k=1}^M \frac{1}{k^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{3\pi^2}{80} \ln \ln x + O(1). \end{aligned}$$

For using the same methods, we can also prove that the theorem holds for all integers $k = 1, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9$. This completes the proof of our theorem.

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